

Open Science in U.S. Magnetic Fusion Research

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Executive summary of proposed strategic elements:

Proposed strategic element #1: The Department of Energy (DOE) Fusion Energy Sciences (FES) program should invest in the development of a community-driven open source software framework for plasma physics research and education. This package should contain the base functionality needed by most plasma physicists along with the functionality needed specifically by the burning plasma research community. Code development should follow best practices for scientific computing^{1,2} including readability and maintainability, version control, continuous integration testing, and pre-merge code reviews. The creation of such a package will improve the reliability and reproducibility of results, and reduce the time needed to achieve scientific understanding. This package should be developed in cooperation with plasma physicists in heliophysics, space physics, and astronomy to maximize the scientific return and allow fusion scientists to benefit from the experience of disciplines that have successfully developed their own community software packages.

Proposed strategic element #2: Science-quality data from fusion devices funded by DOE should be made publicly available within six months after data collection. Each experiment should provide a data analysis guide. Metadata should include log information to advise users on complicating factors such as instrumental artifacts. These data sets should be stored in a format such as HDF5 that is suitable for very long-term archiving while remaining compatible with MDSplus. Each data set should have its own digital object identifier so that it is citable and easily retrievable. FES should support the creation of a centralized portal that can be used to access experimental data. This portal should publish its application programming interface so that data can be accessed by independent software packages.

Scientific and/or engineering opportunity:

In recent years, scientists in several disciplines have developed Python packages that contain core functionality needed by most people in their respective fields. Packages such as Astropy and SunPy have fundamentally transformed how research is performed by providing shared routines for common tasks and a focal point for new contributions. It is no longer necessary for each student or scientist to write their own data analysis package. Plasma physics is at a serious disadvantage compared to these fields because it lacks a fully open source general purpose software ecosystem in a high level language. Given the importance of reproducibility and open science, a transition to open source software is vital. To address this major gap, several scientists have recently begun open development of PlasmaPy: a core Python package for plasma physics.^{3,4} A package like this would fully satisfy the goals in proposed strategic element #1.

Open access to data is the norm in fields such as solar physics and astronomy. One need only glance

¹ G. Wilson, D. A. Aruliah, C. T. Brown et al. (2014), *Best Practices in Scientific Computing*, PLOS Biology, 12, e1001745, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001745>, 2014.

² Software Carpentry website, <https://software-carpentry.org/>

³ N. A. Murphy & Y.-M. Huang, *PlasmaPy: beginning a community developed Python package for plasma physics*, Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163752>

⁴ The PlasmaPy GitHub repository is at: <https://github.com/PlasmaPy/plasmapy>

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through an issue of the Astrophysical Journal to find papers that would not have been written if access to data was restricted in some way. Open data policies for fusion science will increase the scientific return on investment by improving reproducibility and transparency of results; enhancing participation by students and scientists who do not have direct access to experimental devices; motivating improvements to the quality of data and documentation; and allowing for science to happen that would not have happened otherwise.

1. Ensuring U.S. leadership in a field of plasma physics and/or fusion development

Strategic element #1 will allow the U.S. to lead the development of a software package that has the potential to be used by plasma physicists worldwide. The U.S. also has the opportunity to set the standard for the international magnetic fusion research community on experimental data sharing. An open data policy will allow experimental results be analyzed much more thoroughly, leading to more scientific results and publications using data from U.S. devices.

2. Impact on present and future international activities and collaborations by U.S. scientists

Both proposed strategic elements will strongly benefit international activities and collaborations. An open source community software package for plasma physics will naturally lead to international collaboration. Such a package will be helpful for plasma researchers worldwide, who will be able to contribute feedback and code improvements. Making data publicly available may create new international partnerships since researchers worldwide may seek out collaborations with the domestic experimentalists who initially took the data.

3. Impact on the health of domestic fusion research at universities, national labs, and industry

An open source core package for plasma physics will significantly reduce barriers to entry for newcomers and will contribute to a culture of sharing code and data. Students at universities will benefit from learning high level languages and coding best practices which will help them whether they stay in fusion science or find a job in another field. Open data policies will make it easier for students and scientists at institutions without experiments to access and analyze world class data.

4. Impact of/from unanticipated events or innovations requiring programmatic re-direction

Both of the proposed strategic elements are extremely malleable. Modular programming using modern best practices will straightforwardly allow extensions to new devices. A community software package could respond quickly to new innovations.

Additional Considerations:

Muna et al.⁵ estimate that it would take 23 full-time developers working for about 2.5 years to reproduce the ~215,000 lines in the Astropy codebase. While some of this effort will be spread out across the plasma physics community, the efficacy of such a package will be increased greatly by having a team of at least ~5 core developers who will also assist new users in using and contributing to the code. A partnership among DOE, NSF, and NASA would be mutually beneficial.

The effort required to create and maintain a centralized portal or repository for experimental data will likely be comparable to the effort required to create and maintain the Virtual Solar Observatory.⁶

⁵ D. Muna and 153 co-authors, *The Astropy Problem*, [arXiv:1610.03159](https://arxiv.org/abs/1610.03159), 2016.

⁶ Virtual Solar Observatory website, <https://sdac.virtualsolar.org/cgi/search>